

HISTOPATHOLOGICAL CHANGES IN GILLS OF GROUPEL, *EPINEPHELUS COIODES* ASSOCIATED WITH GILL PARASITES

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Abstrak: Kajian histopatologi ke atas insang ikan kerapu *Epinephelus coioides* telah menunjukkan terdapat jangkitan tinggi oleh parasit monogenea diplectanid dan sejenis parasit yang belum dikenal pasti. Parasit monogenea diplectanid telah merangsangkan perubahan hyperplasia pada epithelia lamella, walau bagaimanapun hyperplasia yang serius berserta dengan cantuman lamella dan kehilangan struktur dikaitkan dengan kehadiran parasit yang belum dikenal pasti di dalam kapilari darah insang. Kehadiran sel-sel bersifat eosinofilik dengan bintik hitam dan badan dikelilingi silia mata pada parasit tersebut menunjukkan kemungkinan ia adalah jangkitan salah satu peringkat fluk darah.

Abstract: Histopathological study of the gill tissue of grouper *Epinephelus coioides* revealed high intensities of parasitic infection by diplectanid monogenean and an unidentified parasite. The diplectanid monogenean seemed to cause a mild hyperplasia in the lamella epithelium, while extensive hyperplasia, lamellae fusion and loss of lamellar structures were closely associated with the presence of an unidentified parasite in the gill capillaries. The eosinophilic nature with the presence of black eye-spots and ciliated body indicative of a possible blood fluke.

INTRODUCTION

The grouper, *Epinephelus coioides* is one of the important marine commercial species being cultured in Malaysia. To date only few observations have been made on its parasitic fauna in the cage culture condition (Leong 1992, Ruangpan 1992, Arthur and Lumanlan-Mayo 1997). Two main groups of diplectanid and capsalid monogeneans parasites had been studied in grouper (Leong 1994, Leong and Wong 1993). Four species (*Pseudorhabdosynochus latesi*, *P. monosquamodiscusi*, *P. epinepheli* and *Diplectanum penangi*) within the family Diplectanidae have been reported in South East Asia. Histopathological changes in grouper associated with viral infection (Chua *et al.* 1994, Danayadol *et al.* 1997) and in sleepy grouper disease (Hla Bu and Leong 1997) have been reported. During an epidemiological study in cage cultures at Bkt. Tambun, Penang, the gills of grouper were found to be heavily infected with diplectanid monogeneans. A further study was then

carried out to determine the histopathological changes caused by the parasite.

Eleven moribound groupers (*E. coioides*) were collected from the culture site at Bkt. Tambun, Penang. They varied in size, from 40 – 50 g in body weight and 11 – 14 cm in body length. The fish were sacrificed by pitching method before the gills were removed and placed in petri dish containing 0.85% normal saline for fresh examination of parasite. For histopathology, gill tissues were fixed in 10% buffered formalin for 24 – 48 hours, followed by storage in 70% alcohol and later processed for paraffin sectioning before staining with haematoxylin and eosin (H & E). The histo-logical techniques were based on Humason (1979). The presence of parasitic infection was confirmed through examination of the fresh smear or scrapping of the gill under the compound microscope.

Grossly, the moribound fish showed white blotch lesions on the abdominal area and forehead. The gill filaments showed ischaemic areas. Fresh examination of gills showed that

all of the groupers were infected with diplectanid monogeneans. Histopathological studies indicated that most of the gill tissues sections were infected with the monogeneans and unidentified parasites. These unidentified parasites which were seen as basophilic staining foreign bodies in the blood vessels of gills. Most of the monogeneans were observed in between the secondary lamella (Figure 1). They seemed to cause only minimal tissue reaction, which were represented by a slight hyperplasia of lamella epithelium. In most instances, interstitial tissues edema were seen on the site of infection. The presence of basophilic staining foreign bodies, with concurrent epithelial hyperplasia, lamellae fusion or clubbing and loss of lamella structures were the most significant findings. Most of these bodies were located at the base of the secondary lamella. The basophilic staining foreign bodies were roundish in structure, with a diameter of 7.70 – 15.84 μm (n=9) and the bodies were located inside lacunae having a diameter of 18.70 – 33.61 μm (n=9). Similar foreign bodies, with black eye spots and cilia surrounding the body, but eosinophilic in nature having a diameter of 14.95 – 21.06 μm (n=7) were also seen in the

same gills filament (Figure 2). Diameter size for their lacunae were between 32.26 – 42.09 μm (n=7).

A density of approximately 27-54 monogeneans were observed from a 5 μm section of single gill filament (n=20). At this infection density which was higher than the number in diseased groupers as was reported earlier by Leong and Wong (1988), the heavy load of parasites could have lead to stressful condition and caused the fish to succumb to mortality. This probably explained the persistent daily mortality reported on the sampling site as highlighted by Leong and Wong (1990). The main histopathological changes for monogenean infection were found to be hyperplasia and interstitial tissue edema, where epithelial cells greatly increased in number at the secondary and primary lamella (Takashi 1984). This hyperplasia of epithelial cells at the base and length of the lamellae could be due to physical irritation caused by the opisthaptor (hold-fast) or squamodish and suckers as the parasites anchored at the gills probably for food (Ferguson 1989). No haemorrhage was observed in the tissue in the infection site.

Figure 1: Infected gill filaments with monogeneans ().H & E, x10. Bar = 5 μm .

Figure 2: Monogenean hook () were seen encapsulated within the gill lamellae. Note hyperplasia and lamellar fusion of the filament on the site of infection. H & E. x40. Bar = 5 μ m.

In addition, most of the gills sections showed the presence of foreign bodies within the filament blood vessels, indicating possibility of blood parasitism. There were marked epithelial hyperplasia and loss of lamellar structure in the area. The eosinophilic nature with cilia and black eye spots of these foreign bodies resembled that of blood fluke miracidia. In contrast, the basophilic staining foreign bodies could be their dead remnants. According to Herbert *et al.* (1994), eggs and miracidia of *Cruoricola lates* from sea bass could cause hyperplasia, haemorrhage and clumping of gill filaments, on the other hand no haemorrhage were seen in miracidium infection of *Cardicola alsae* (Meade and Pratt 1965). The blood fluke infection, especially the eggs and miracidium stages, could cause mortality in cultured fish (Wallace 1974a, Hoffman *et al.* 1985, Herbert *et al.* 1994). However, the results from our observation cannot be ascertained if the blood fluke infection in grouper could cause mortality, even though blood flukes were found in the cultured sea bass (Herbert *et al.*

1991) and grouper (Leong, personal communication).

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